

Pediatric Early Warning Scores (PEWS) Tool Implementation

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Background

- Children that are sick need to be monitored closely, so that signs and symptoms of distress can be caught early before a child's condition deteriorates.
- When a child becomes ill, especially with a respiratory illness, they are at risk of deteriorating quickly and may die.
- Many times, the child's symptoms are unrecognized because a clinician may not be proficient at assessment.

Purpose Statement

To facilitate the implementation of the Pediatrics Early Pediatrics Warning Scores (PEWS) tool for use in a general pediatric unit:

- Assess aspirations, strengths, barriers, and resources to using the tool.
- Develop strategies focused on systematic implementation.
- Assess nurses' utilization of the tool after implementation.

Methods

Quality Improvement Project using IHI Improvement Model & Utilizing PDSA to implement & test changes in practice

Setting

- 600-bed acute care hospital located in Southern California.
- 25- inpatient beds and four observational outpatient beds on a pediatric unit

Conceptual Framework- PDSA - Institute of Health Improvement (IHI)

PDSA Cycle Ramps: Sequential Building of Knowledge

The Model for Improvement

Focus Group Team Input

SOAR ANALYSIS MODEL

STRENGTHS	OPPORTUNITIES	ASPIRATION	RESULTS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nursing staff highly motivated to use tool • Motivated nurses' team • Motivated doctors' team • Leadership support 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide better patient care. • Create systematic policies that everyone can follow. • Standardized patient care • Easy to navigate electronic charting flowsheet for PEWS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Best practiced: Implement, assess, and care. • Improve patient outcomes. • Improve communication. • Provide care based on evidence. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The quality Improvement project being adapted on the pediatric unit • Policies and standard of practice developed to support the ongoing use of the tool • Information Technology (IT) creates an efficient navigation process in the electronic chart

Implementation Plan

Evaluation Plan

- Ongoing chart audit
- Monitor plan of action implemented for higher PEWS scores
- Monitor number of cases escalated to higher level of care

Challenges/Outcome

Challenges

- Focus group unable to meet on a regular basis
- The Covid-19 pandemic played a major part in group participants due to changes in their work schedules
- Start date of implementation delayed due to hospital staff changes
- Additional time had to be set up for doctors to have the education

Outcomes

- Improved assessment skill using the PEWS tool
- Clear Communication: clinicians speaking from the same mental model
- Consistent utilization of PEWS

Recommendations

- Ongoing chart audits
- Yearly competency evaluation
- New hires education
- Float pool staff education
- Policy and standard of care development

References

